

D10.1 Quantity of Access Offered – TA3

Version 1.0 (final)

Date 23 December 2022

Grant Agreement number: 823914

Project acronym: ARIADNEplus

Project title: Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe - plus

Funding Scheme: H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1

**Project co-ordinator name,
Title and Organisation:** Prof. Franco Niccolucci, PIN Scrl - Polo Universitario "Città di Prato"

Tel: +39 0574 602578

E-mail: franco.niccolucci@pin.unifi.it

Project website address: www.ariadne-infrastructure.eu

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Programme (H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1) under grant agreement n° 823914.

Author: **Carlo Meghini, CNR**
Contributing partners: **Sheena Bassett, PIN**
Quality Control **Paola Ronzino, PIN**

Document History

- 02.12.2022 – Draft Version 0.1
- 08.12.2022 – Draft Version 0.2
- 18.12.2022 – Final version 1.0

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons CC-BY License. To view a copy of the license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Table of Contents

- 1. Executive Summary 5**
- 2. Introduction and Objectives 6**
 - 2.1 About the Transnational Access Training Programme 6
 - 2.2 Ensuring the quality of candidates..... 6
 - 2.3 Implementing Interoperability objectives..... 7
- 3. TNA Dissemination, evaluation and offers 8**
- 4. Candidate projects 9**
- 5. Overview of training provided 12**
 - 5.1 Implementing Interoperability Summer School..... 12
 - 5.2 Schedule overview and details..... 13
- 6. Evaluation of the Feedback..... 14**
 - 6.1 Feedback Summary 14
 - 6.2 Detailed Feedback from Attendees 14
- 7. Conclusions 16**
- Annexes 17**
 - Guidelines for TNA Evaluators 17
 - Introductory Slides from the Summer School..... 18

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the Trans National Access (TNA) activities carried out during the ARIADNEplus project within Work Package 10 (WP10) by CNR and describes the results achieved by this work package. CNR were responsible for the delivery of TNA entitled “Implementing Interoperability” at their premises in Pisa, Italy. The first call was intended from 2020 onwards but the pandemic restrictions stopped travel. No further activities could be undertaken until 2021 when it was decided to organise the TNA as four Summer Schools and all previously accepted applicants were offered (and took up) places on the week-long courses.

All candidates had to send in application forms describing their projects and how these would benefit from the use of the training. One of three independent reviewers evaluated the applications and awarded a mark and recommendation to ensure the quality and relevance of the training for the applicants. All the applications were accepted, the majority being evaluated with the highest rating.

The training had to address a wide range of interests as well as varying levels of knowledge, the project descriptions demonstrating the need for interoperability and future reuse of data.

The goal of the Summer School was to enable researchers and professionals with the management of their datasets with a focus on interoperability, whether creating these from scratch and/or dealing with existing or legacy data within the context of their project. In terms of the numbers, nine of the 15 places were filled, i.e. 60%. Considering that the original plan was to run at least two Summer Schools and that not everyone was prepared to return to in-person activities immediately after travel restrictions were lifted, this is a reasonable achievement in line with expectations.

Finally, each student was asked to complete feedback forms after completing their TNA placements. In general, the school was well received, as it can be appreciated from the detailed feedback provided by most of the students. Ontologies are nowadays widely employed both for domain specific modelling and for data integration, but there is no adequate knowledge about them, especially in the disciplines of the Humanities. When exposed to the basic principles of ontology-based modelling, young researchers in the Humanities are prompt to grasp the main concepts, since almost all of them have been exposed to philosophy and have confronted large and articulated conceptual schemas. Once the basics are understood, it does not take much to learn the tools to apply these technologies.

During the lectures, students asked many questions, both theoretical on ontologies and knowledge representation in general, and specific to their projects, which they had the opportunity to present during the first lecture.

2. Introduction and Objectives

2.1 About the Transnational Access Training Programme

The ARIADNEplus TNA Training Programme was originally planned as up to three annual calls for individual/team training for:

- Mapping Existing Datasets to CIDOC-CRM (at PIN, Prato, Italy), and
- Individual training: Data Stewardship (UoY ADS, York, UK).

The first of these calls was issued in September 2019 with visits by candidates planned for between January and June 2020, with subsequent calls to be issued in 2020 and 2021 until the maximum capacity on each course had been reached. This was 15 user weeks (75 days) for PIN and 7 user weeks (35 days) for ADS.

Two further courses were offered as week-long Summer Schools by CNR, Pisa, Italy:

- Visual Media for the Documentation of Fieldwork and Artefacts, and
- Implementing Interoperability.

The Summer Schools were planned for 2021 with the expectation (based upon previous experience) that most of the places offered, 10 and 15 weeks, respectively, were likely to be taken up in one year but with the contingency that a second set could be offered in 2022 if not.

However, the global COVID-19 pandemic and national lock-downs severely disrupted the TNA Programme as travel was restricted from spring 2020 and the situation only began to improve in 2021 with the roll-out of national vaccination programmes and reduced restrictions which allowed people to start travelling again. Consequently, the programme was revised to allow as many as possible researchers to apply and attend. All training was offered as four Summer Schools between May and July 2022 with first priority given to previously accepted applicants who were unable to attend their original placements.

2.2 Ensuring the quality of candidates

In order to provide quality training, the students attending the TNA courses had to be suitably qualified and undertaking relevant projects and research. Consequently, an independent panel of external experts was formed and the applications from each student sent to a member of the panel for review and evaluation. The external evaluators were:

- Milica Tapavički-Ilić, Institute of Archaeology, Belgrade, Serbia
- Ivana Pandzic, University of Banja Luka, Bosnia Herzegovina
- David Bibby, Heritage Office, Stuttgart, Germany.

In addition, three senior ARIADNEplus members involved in the TNA delivery also received the applications and evaluations to ensure they agreed with the recommendations.

The three external evaluators were provided with a set of guidelines (see Annex A) for performing this task, each returning a written summary for the candidates they were asked to assess.

2.3 Implementing Interoperability objectives

The Implementing Interoperability Summer School was offered as part of the TNA Training Programme for 2022.

Work Package objectives

- To provide support in dataset design and implementation,
- To provide support for multimedia management of archaeological datasets.

The goal of this Summer School was to enable researchers and professionals with the management of their datasets with a focus on interoperability, whether creating these from scratch and/or dealing with existing or legacy data within the context of their project. The approach is based on the semantic web standards such as RDF, RDF Schema, SPARQL and OWL. Issues that were to be addressed included integration of datasets, semantic annotation, mapping to metadata schemas, use of standards and dealing with formats that are no longer supported. The Summer School started with a review of the participants individual research questions so that the topics covered in the summer school met each student's requirements. Experts were on hand to provide guidance and advice and help each student to develop their skills by applying them to their own datasets during the sessions during which supervised access to the laboratory facilities was provided. The final results were reviewed at the end of the summer school so that each student could continue to apply their new-found knowledge to further developing their datasets.

3. TNA Dissemination, evaluation and offers

The second TNA call for the Summer Schools was issued mid-February 2022 (<https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/summer-schools-2022/>). These were as follows:

- Data Stewardship – ADS, University of York, UK. Online on Wednesdays 4th, 11th, 18th, 25th May and 1st June 2022.
- Mapping Existing Datasets to CIDOC CRM – PIN Scrl., Prato, Tuscany, Italy. Monday 20th–Friday 24th June 2022.
- Visual Media for the Documentation of Fieldwork and Artefacts – CNR, Pisa, Italy. Monday 27th June–Friday 1st July 2022.
- Implementing Interoperability – CNR, Pisa, Italy. Monday 4th–Friday 8th July 2022.

All four Summer Schools were promoted through the usual channels and also on the DARIAH Digital Humanities Course Register. At the same time, all the previously accepted candidates who had not received their training were contacted and asked if they would like to attend the corresponding Summer School instead.

There were nine candidates who applied for places on for the *Implementing Interoperability Summer School* and whom were all offered places.

Name	Institution	Country
Jamie Bradley	ADS, Uni York	UK
Teagan Zoldoske	ADS, Uni York	UK
Jamie Geddes	ADS, Uni York	UK
Sabina Batlle Baró	Universitat de Barcelona	Spain
Jo (Josephine) Gilham	ADS, Uni York	UK
Mia Trentin	CYI	Cyprus
Valentina Vassallo	CYI	Cyprus
Vera Moitinho Almeida	University of Porto	Portugal
Tugce Karatas*	University of Turin	Italy

As Tugce Karatas was from an Italian University, she was self-funded as she was not eligible for a bursary.

4. Candidate projects

This section provides an overview of each of the candidates' proposed projects as outlined in their application forms in order to illustrate the variety of applications being catered for and the specific interests covered.

Adding resources to the ARIADNEplus knowledge base (Jamie Bradley, Jo Gilham, ADS)

I joined the Archaeology Data Service as Lead Applications Developer in January 2022 and am seeking to extend my understanding of how information science can be used in the heritage sector. I have started work on ARIADNE and also on a UK project on interoperability of marine data resources, so understanding this field is a key CPD priority for me. I particularly want to understand how data in ARIADNE is aggregated and transformed in the ARIADNE knowledgebase and triplestore.

Likewise, Jo Gilham is working on an implementation of an instance of the ARIADNE portal for at the ADS and will use the training in her further work on the OASIS project.

Dissemination of archaeology data within High Speed 2 (Teagan Zoldoske, ADS)

High Speed Two (HS2) is one of the largest modern infrastructure projects in England which will deliver a rail route between London and Birmingham whilst also overall increasing capacity of the rail network. As such, it presents an unprecedented opportunity to explore Britain's past through the country's largest ever linear infrastructure project. The sheer scale of discoveries, the geographical span of the project and the vast range of our history unearthed makes HS2's historic environment programme a unique chance to tell the story of Britain's past. The scale of this data is both its greatest assets and one of the most difficult parts.

My attendance at the summer school would have several objectives:

1. A better understanding of the methods and approaches employed in making disparate archaeological data interoperable, including integration of datasets, semantic annotation, mapping to metadata schemas, use of standards and dealing with formats that are no longer supported.
2. Understanding of how data is disseminated through other outputs such as ARIADNEplus
3. Creating a better idea of other methods used for the dissemination of large quantities of data and how this information can be applied to and better High Speed 2.

Understanding 3DHOP viewer and mapping resources to ARIADNEplus knowledgebase (Jamie Geddes, ADS)

I have started working on major projects such as UNPATH waters project on interoperability of marine data resources and have worked on some aspects of HS2 data, so learning new ways to share datasets and become more interoperable are vital in my role. I have also been working on major archives such as the Tracing the Past project archive that has involved the usage of 3d laser scan data and presenting the data in 3DHOP. I need to understand 3M mapping of data and how data in ARIADNE is aggregated and transformed in the ARIADNE knowledge base.

Muntanya viva: assentaments, recursos i paisatges a la Catalunya Medieval (s. IV-XIII) (Sabina Batlle Baró, Universitat de Barcelona)

The main research objectives of this projects are the study and analysis of the historicarchaeological information of the Tremp-Montsec area (an important part of the Orígens UNESCO Global Geopark). The main goal is to localize, identify and study the human settlements. Up to now, the excavation, interpretation, and study of these sites have enabled us to reconstruct the medieval history of this quite unknown region, from the 5th to the 15th century. The new data that are created and collected every year in the new excavations and surveys, together with the legacy data and the data coming from historical documentation, will help design new interpretative models on the evolution of the population in this area, as well as the patterns and morphology of the typical settlements within this geographical and chronological frame. All of this will be made in close collaboration with landscape studies, to build an interpretation on the historical landscape in mountainous areas. There are multiple and heterogenous datasets created and managed within the project, and these include field data from different sites, 3D models, artifacts' data, etc. Now, these datasets are neither interconnected nor described, and our goal is to properly enrich these data with the necessary metadata to make them reusable, either by researchers within the project or outside it.

DIGItizing GRAffiti: methodology definition for the study of Cypriot Historic Graffiti (Mia Trentin and Valentina Vassallo, CYI)

The overall objective of DIGIGRAF is to fill the gap in the field of graffiti study through the definition and establishment of good practices for the documentation, analysis and study of the graffiti heritage in Cyprus. More specifically,

- addressing the scientific community, the project aims to create an innovative open access repository and a reference methodology to promote the use of graffiti as a historical source suitable in different fields of study. DIGIGRAF will represent an advancement in the field of Digital Cultural Heritage, enhancing the present knowledge concerning the application of digital tools.
- addressing the general public, the project aims to raise awareness on graffiti heritage and to promote their preservation within the island and abroad, through communication activities.

The research aim is to define a methodology, based on integrated digital, imaging and analytical approaches, able to document and describe in a holistic way all aspects concerning graffiti, from the context to their materiality, historical interpretation and conservation state. This will provide

structured data to be shared by scholars of different disciplines as well as exploited to foster the knowledge of Cypriot cultural graffiti heritage within local communities and tourists.

Mapping a 3D archaeological pottery database to CIDOC-CRM (Vera Moitinho Almeida, University of Porto)

The aim of this project is to develop the mapping of existing 3D archaeological pottery datasets from collections in Portugal (ongoing project for a museum exhibition) and the ODEEG project (concluded) to the CIDOC CRM standard, namely to integrate them into a wider framework such as the ARIADNE Infrastructure.

Some of the potentialities of working with 3D digital data in archaeology are already well-known. The number of online databases providing open-access to 3D datasets and aggregators linking to 3D open data of CH objects for research has increased in the last decades. Concerning online databases with 3D models of ancient pottery, low resolution models are typically available, possibly mainly for fast visualisation purposes. However, crucial data, such as, raw data, high-resolution data, and corresponding technical metadata – also for repeatability and reproducibility of the data, much needed for a rapidly growing number of scientific works – seems to be overall neglected.

At the end, the goal is to provide a wide variety of meaningful, searchable, citable, and reusable data for researchers. This is to say, a solid basis for distinct types of archaeological and other scientific research including, but not limited to: chronological and regional differentiation of vessel shapes, dimensions, and capacities; pottery manufacturing and function; ancient measuring systems; as well as knowledge, cultural, social, and economical networks.

Digital Data Curation For Archaeology Through Semantic Encoding (Tugce Karatas, University of Turin)

Digital curation in cultural heritage organisations has become more and more established as empirical research for tools, techniques, skills, and standards for making curators able to manage the related digital data. It supports specific applications in diverse contexts of cultural heritage management. My project addresses the archaeological domain, a particular challenge since projects span from the planning of the excavations to the analysis of the findings, their interpretation, and the display of the results in a final exhibition. Further, in archaeology, digital curation must account for the relationship between physical materials and their digital twins. My approach formulates a comprehensive definition of digital curation for the archaeological domain and devises a unified model based on the semantic organisation of the data in order to apply the model to semantic-born archaeological projects as well as the existing archaeological datasets. It will show how the archaeological activities carried out and have been supported by the semantically encoded digital curation by describing the conceptualization of the archaeological, archaeometric, and cataloguing knowledge, which leads to the design of the database schema and its employment in a content management system for the monitoring of the activities of the archaeological projects. We will examine the CMS Omeka-S and the guidelines and recommendations for the usage of the platform when annotating the metadata.

5. Overview of training provided

This section summarises the training provided to the TNA Summer School candidates.

5.1 Implementing Interoperability Summer School

Venue: Area della Ricerca di Pisa, Via G. Moruzzi 1, 56124, Pisa, Italy.

Period: 4th-8th July 2022

Description of the TNA offered

This Summer School aims at providing students with an introduction to metadata design for archaeological datasets, with perspective content provided as case studies by the students. The school will consist of some introductory lectures followed by hands-on seminars in which the design is developed by the students with the supervision of ISTI experts and then collectively discussed.

Programme

The goal of this Summer School is to enable researchers and professionals with the management of their datasets with a focus on interoperability, whether creating these from scratch and/or dealing with existing or legacy data within the context of their project. The approach is based on the semantic web standards such as RDF, RDF Schema, SPARQL and OWL. Issues that may be addressed will include integration of datasets, semantic annotation, mapping to metadata schemas, use of standards and dealing with formats that are no longer supported. The Summer School will start with a review of the participants individual research questions so that the topics covered in the summer school meet each student's requirements. Experts will be on hand to provide guidance and advice and each student will develop their skills by applying them to their own datasets during the sessions which will provide supervised access to the laboratory facilities. The final results will be reviewed at the end of the summer school so that each student can continue to apply their new-found knowledge to further developing their datasets.

Pre-requisites: General knowledge of archaeological data management but usually with a non-technical background.

5.2 Schedule overview and details

	Monday July 4	Tuesday July 5	Wednesday July 6	Thursday July 7	Friday July 8
Morning 9:30 - 12:30		RDF and RDF Schema	Ontology Web Language	Semantic Data Integration	Architecture and tools for Linked Data
Afternoon 14:30 - 17.30	Presentation and introduction	The SPARQL query Language	The CIDOC CRM	Hands-on	

Monday, July 4, Room C29

Morning: left free to allow participants to travel

Afternoon: Introduction¹ to the programme of the School. Candidates will have the opportunity to present their projects and their learning objectives. Lecturer: Carlo Meghini, CNR ISTI

Tuesday, July 5, Room C40 (morning) and Room C29 (afternoon)

Morning: Introduction to the web and to the semantic web. The Resource Description Framework. Semantic modeling and the RDF Schema vocabulary. Lecturer: Carlo Meghini, CNR ISTI

Afternoon: The SPARQL language for manipulating RDF data. Inferences. Lecturer: Carlo Meghini, CNR ISTI

Wednesday, July 6, Room C29

Morning: Introduction to ontologies and to the Ontology Web Language. Lecturer: Carlo Meghini, CNR ISTI.

Afternoon: Introduction to the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model and to its usage in archaeological data modeling. Lecturer: Maria Theodoridou, FORTH.

Thursday, July 7, Room C29

Morning: Semantic Data Integration. Lecturer: Maria Theodoridou, FORTH.

Afternoon: Hands-on: Application of 3M to the data of the participants. Lecturer: Maria Theodoridou, FORTH.

Friday, July 8, Room C29

Morning: This lecture will present an architecture based on open-source software for managing Linked Data and will discuss relevant issues in creating and managing Linked Data datasets. Lecturer: Cesare Concordia, CNR ISTI.

Afternoon: this is left free to allow participants to travel.

¹ See Annex 9.2 for the Introduction presentation for the Summer School.

6. Evaluation of the Feedback

Each of the participants was required to complete a feedback form after they had completed their TNA training. The results of the feedback is summarised here for the Summer School.

6.1 Feedback Summary

In general, the school was well received, as it can be appreciated from the detailed feedback provided in the next section by most of the students.

Ontologies are nowadays widely employed both for domain specific modelling and for data integration, but there is no adequate knowledge about them, especially in the disciplines of the Humanities. When exposed to the basic principles of ontology-based modelling, young researchers in the Humanities are prompt to grasp the main concepts, since almost all of them have been exposed to philosophy and have confronted large and articulated conceptual schemas. Once the basics are understood, it does not take much to learn the tools to apply these technologies.

During the lectures, students asked many questions, both theoretical on ontologies and knowledge representation in general, and specific to their projects, which they had the opportunity to present during the first lecture.

Because there was a lot to cover, the number of examples given was limited and one student felt she would like more. Another student suggested extending the school to two weeks, so as to be able to cover every topic in more detail.

6.2 Detailed Feedback from Attendees

The responses are reported below, but anonymised for data protection reasons.

1. *Main achievements experienced during the training:* Learned a lot about ontologies, RDF/Turtle have become clear and understandable.

Suggestions how to improve visits/access: None

Main achievements experienced during the training: No suggestion, was great.

Suggestions how to improve TNA: No suggestion, was great

2. *Main achievements experienced during the training:* Better understanding of linked data and triple-based database structures.

Suggestions how to improve visits/access: Foster better opportunities to create organic discussions amongst the participants. All staying in the same hotel, meals together, etc.

Suggestions how to improve TNA: none.

3. *Main achievements experienced during the training:* Learned about ontologies, with examples from CIDOC/CRM and AO-Cat, some information about importing triples and SPARQL queries.

Difficulties encountered: would have liked more practical experience with SPARQL and triple stores.

Suggestions how to improve visits/access: None

Suggestions how to improve TNA: None.

4. *Main achievements experienced during the training:* I achieved the following expertise during the TNA: metadata design to and to apply it to the DIGIGRAF project repository; to develop a specific metadata structure based on the graffiti ontology we developed; how to develop an interoperable and semantic structure able to include the different kind of graffiti data (images, panoramic models, RTI, 3d laser scanning, hand traced copies, etc.).

Suggestions how to improve visits/access: None

Suggestions how to improve TNA: None.

5. *Main achievements experienced during the training:* I have gained further theoretical and practical knowledge from leading experts, enhanced my skills, and enlarged my network of contacts – which I hope may lead to new collaborations and to the development of innovative future projects. The Summer School was very well organised. Suggestion: It was an interesting Summer School. However, considering the complexity of the topics, perhaps the training would benefit from extending its duration 1 more week – i.e., a 2-week Summer School, where the 1st week would be as it was and the 2nd week completely hands-on, working with our own data (and with the support and discussions from experts and colleagues).

Suggestions how to improve visits/access: None

Suggestions how to improve TNA: None.

7. Conclusions

As a means of providing as much training as possible in the final year with the resources available, all TNA was offered as Summer Schools. It is obviously a bit more difficult to meet everyone's needs when dealing with several different sets of requirements and levels of technical knowledge within a limited time period but, overall, everyone seemed satisfied that they had learnt enough from the course to apply it to their projects. In terms of the numbers, nine of the 15 places were filled, i.e. 60%. Considering that the original plan was to run at least two Summer Schools and that not everyone was prepared to return to in-person activities immediately after travel restrictions were lifted, this is a reasonable achievement in line with expectations.

In general, the school was well received, as it can be appreciated from the detailed feedback provided by the students. The basic problem was to understand the principles of ontology-based modelling, which is becoming a widely employed tool in both for domain specific modelling and for data integration also in the Humanities. The School responded to this problem by giving students a detailed account of the fundamental techniques, which the students were prompt to grasp as witnessed by their feedback. Once the basics were understood, it did not take much to learn the tools to apply them.

Annexes

Guidelines for TNA Evaluators

The selection panel is responsible for:

- Assessing the proposals for transnational access received in response to open calls, based on the following selection criteria:
 - o Quality of the applicant,
 - o Scientific merit of the case study or individual research project proposed by the applicant,
 - o Potential benefit to the applicant from the training on offer.
- Applying the principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality to the selection process,
- Attending to gender equality.

Priority will be given to:

- Users who have not previously been awarded ARIADNE resources,
- Early career researchers,
- Researchers working in countries without comparable facilities/opportunities.

Each panel member should indicate his/her evaluation decision by indicating Accept/Reject on the application, providing a short explanation. For positive evaluations, priority should be expressed with a value from one to four (four being the highest score).

The Project Coordinator and the Deputy Coordinator will express the final decision, based on the selection criteria (see above).

Applications from researchers belonging to an ARIADNEplus partner institution are allowed and encouraged, unless they are based on the home country of the institution offering the TNA.

Eligibility criteria (to be checked by the TNA manager)

To be eligible for ARIADNEplus TNA funding, researchers need to comply with the following criteria:

- Work or be registered as a student in an institution in an EU Member State or an Associate State; researchers from institutions in the home country of the TNA opportunity are not eligible to receive an ARIADNEplus TNA bursary.
- Agree to provide feedback on TNA opportunity by:
 - o Completing an ARIADNEplus user report and returning it to TNAcontact@ariadne-infrastructure.eu,
 - o Completing the European Commission's User group questionnaire using the online form.
- Agree to their names being included in a list of ARIADNEplus TNA users provided to the European Commission and published in various media, including the Internet.
- Disseminate results obtained as a result of TNA access as widely as possible and provide ARIADNEplus with the details. Publications should include the following acknowledgement: The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Commission under the H2020 Programme, contract no. H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1-823914 (ARIADNEplus).

Introductory Slides from the Summer School

ARIADNEplus Summer School
“Implementing Interoperability”
Pisa, July 4-8, 2022

Introduction

Carlo Meghini

Outlook

- What is Interoperability
 - Data Interoperability
- Achieving Semantic Data Interoperability
 - Programme of the course, part one
- Optimized interoperability: data integration
 - Programme of the course, part two

Outlook

- What is Interoperability
 - Data Interoperability
- Achieving Semantic Data Interoperability
 - Programme of the course, part one
- Optimized interoperability: data integration
 - Programme of the course, part two

What is Interoperability

According to Wikipedia, “Interoperability is a characteristic of a product or system to work with other products or systems”.

In computer science, System A interoperates with System B if the execution of some function offered by A includes the execution of some function offered by B. Interoperability means that A and B can cooperate.

Syntactic Interoperability

If two or more systems use common data formats and communication protocols and are capable of communicating with each other, they exhibit **syntactic interoperability**.

- XML and SQL are examples of common data formats and protocols.

Lower-level data formats also contribute to syntactic interoperability, ensuring that alphabetical characters are stored in the same ASCII or a Unicode format in all the communicating systems.

Semantic Interoperability

Beyond the ability of two or more computer systems to exchange information, **semantic interoperability** is the ability to automatically interpret the information exchanged meaningfully and accurately in order to produce useful results as defined by the end users of both systems.

Semantic interoperability is for us the gist of the matter: what really we aim at, because syntactic interoperability is a lot easier.

Basics of interoperability

In the typical scenario, if system A needs to interoperate with system B, it must:

1. Send to B requests that B understands. In particular, the requests must contain data in the format that B expects (*Onward*).
2. Transform the responses that it receives from B into something that it can use. In particular, the data in the responses must be transformed into the format that A needs (*Backward*).

Data Interoperability

The term “data interoperability” is used to refer to interoperability of services that fundamentally concern data, such as data retrieval and access services.

This is what the “I” in “FAIR” means^(*):

The data usually need to be integrated with other data. In addition, the data need to interoperate with applications or workflows for analysis, storage, and processing.

^(*) Fair principles at <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Data Interoperability

With respect to our interoperability scenario, data interoperability concerns system B and aims at facilitating both the onward and the backward side of the interaction:

- Onward: less work (ideally none) to translate A's data into B's format
- Backward: less work (ideally none) to translate B's results into A's format

Data Interoperability

One important aspect of data interoperability is that in most of the cases, the designer of system B *does not know* which system(s) A will want to interoperate with system B data.

- Many of these systems are likely not to exist at the time in which system B is created.

Therefore, *ad hoc* solutions are non-solutions.

Outlook

- What is Interoperability
 - Data Interoperability
- Achieving Semantic Data Interoperability
 - Programme of the course, part one
- Optimized interoperability: data integration
 - Programme of the course, part two

Achieving Semantic Data Interoperability

Guidelines for Data Interoperability (from FAIR principles):

- I1. Data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation*
- I2. Data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles*
- I3. Data include qualified references to other data*

Guidelines for Semantic Data Interoperability:

*CM1. Data are endowed with a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable representation of their **meaning***

Achieving Semantic Data Interoperability

Guidelines for Data Interoperability (from FAIR principles):

*I1. Data use a **formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable** language for knowledge representation*

standard

logic

*I2. Data use **vocabularies** that follow FAIR principles*

knowledge organization systems

*I3. Data include **qualified references** to other data*

based on the web architecture

Guidelines for Semantic Data Interoperability:

*CM1. Data are endowed with a **formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable representation of their meaning***

ontology

Achieving Semantic Data Interoperability

Million dollars question: what is a **standard logic, based on the web architecture**, for representing data, **ontologies** and **knowledge organization systems**?

2-cent answer: the Ontology Web Language.

In fact, the Ontology Web Language are two (OWL DL and OWL Full) and they sit on top of a complex architecture.

Programme of the course, part one

The first part of the course will cover this architecture:

- The web and the semantic web
- RDF, a data model for the web
- RDF Schema, a simpler ontology web language
- SPARQL, a manipulation language for RDF data
- OWL, the Ontology Web Language

Outlook

- What is Interoperability
 - Data Interoperability
- Achieving Semantic Data Interoperability
 - Programme of the course, part one
- Optimized interoperability: data integration
 - Programme of the course, part two

Optimized interoperability: data integration

A Research Infrastructure offers services that over-arch a number of community-oriented service systems.

Each one of these services needs to interoperate with one or more community-oriented services.

The interoperability scenario is therefore shaped like a star:

Optimized interoperability: data integration

For instance, an Infrastructural Resource Discovery service needs to “propagate” the user request to the local community discovery services, in order to find out which services the community has.

Typically, each community has implemented resource discovery based on the local requirements and best practices, resulting in a very heterogeneous landscape.

Each interaction with a local service requires an onward and a backward operation, resulting in a very complex, time-consuming, distributed synchronous computation.

Optimized interoperability: data integration

In order to optimize the execution of the operation, an asynchronous 2-stage approach is followed.

1. The required information is collected from each local source, transformed and loaded into a common repository (*e.g.*, the Catalogue of the Research Infrastructure), asynchronously.
2. The global service executes its operation on the common repository, synchronously.

This strategy is very-well known in distributed computing, and typically relies on a separate infrastructure, known as Aggregation Infrastructure, to carry out the first stage.

Optimized interoperability: data integration

An Aggregation Infrastructure performs Data Integration, to produce common repositories that integrate under a unique conceptual schema the information coming from a variety of local sources.

And we all want these common repositories to be (guess what) ... well, interoperable!

As a consequence, (interoperability-driven) data integration relies on

- A pivot ontology that defines the meaning of the terms used in the common repository
- A series of mappings that transform local data into data structured according to the pivot ontology
- An engine that executes the mappings and creates the common repository

Programme of the course, part two

In the second part of the course, we will cover interoperability-driven data integration:

- The CIDOC CRM, a top ontology for data integration in the CH domain
- The X3ML framework for creating ontology mappings
- Hands-on session on mapping your data to the CRM or to the AO-Cat
- Linked data and tools to handle them (RDF, OWL & SPARQL).